

Design of a Multi-Mode Pipelined Multiplier for Floating-Point Applications

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Abstract - This paper presents the design of a VLSI multi-mode pipelined multiplier. The multiplier is designed to accept three types of operands: IEEE FP double and signal format and 32-bit two's complement integers. The multiplier is fully compliant with the IEEE standard for floating point arithmetic (IEEE-Std-754-1985) with the exception of denormalized numbers. All rounding modes and exception handling are supported. The high performance of the multiplier is made possible by the use of octal Booth encoding of the multiplier to reduce the number of partial products. In addition, a new fast carry adder, the Optimized Carry-Multiplexed (OCM) adder, is used to accelerate the critical carry propagation paths. The multiplier is designed to operate at 40MHz and is pipelined to allow a new operation to begin every clock cycle. Thus, 40 MFLOPS operation is possible in double precision and integer modes. In single precision mode, two operations are performed in parallel yielding 80 MFLOPS performance.

1 Introduction

Many systems in both the military and commercial applications domains require high speed floating point arithmetic. Floating point circuitry tends to be very expensive both in terms of speed of operation and in terms of the amount of circuitry required for the implementation. In this paper, the design of a new multimode multiplier is presented. The multiplier features very high performance along with compliance with the IEEE standard for floating point arithmetic (IEEE Std 754-1985). In addition, the multiplier has three modes of operation defined by the type of operand presented to the multiplier: double precision floating point, single precision floating point and 32-bit 2's complement integer. The multiplier may be used in a stand-alone chip implementation but is small enough

to be included as a macrocell in a floating point processor chip.

The architectural definition and design of the multiplier will be presented first. The discussion will focus on the double precision mode. The single precision and integer mode will be discussed in relation to the double precision case. The pipelining strategy of the multiplier will be covered next followed by a brief overview of the performance of the multiplier.

The architecture of this multiplier is an extension and enhancement of a single mode, double precision multiplier design by CPT. Erik Freitheim (USA) at AFIT in 1988 ([3]). This work was supported by the Air Force Rome Laboratories at Griffiss AFB, New York.

2 Architectural Description

The multiplication of two floating point operands is a five step process:

- Compute output sign bit.
- Multiply mantissas.
- Add exponents.
- Restore standard format.
- Exception detection.

Each of these steps is discussed in detail for the double precision case in the following subsections. The modifications necessary to support the single precision and integer modes is presented thereafter.

2.1 Sign bit computation

If the signs of the two operands are the same, then the output sign bit is '0' corresponding to a positive

Figure 1: Mantissa Array Element

number; otherwise the result is negative and the sign bit is a '1'. This is implemented as a simple exclusive-or gate.

2.2 Mantissa multiplication

The mantissa multiply is much more complex. The format of a double precision number allocates 52 bits to the mantissa. These bits are the fractional part of the mantissa. There is also an assumed '01' immediately to the left of the binary point (the 0 is the sign bit) which completes the fifty-four bit mantissa. The mantissa multiplier is, therefore, a fifty-four bit by fifty-four bit multiply. It is implemented in a parallel fashion, that is, all of the partial products are generated simultaneously and then accumulated in an array of carry-save adders. A binary implementation of this multiplier would require fifty-four partial products. This would be excessive in both the amount of circuitry (size) and the amount of time required to determine the product. The number of partial products can be reduced by a process called Booth encoding.

In Booth encoding, a binary operand of the form

$$b = b_n 2^n + b_{n-1} 2^{n-1} + \dots + b_1 2^1 + b_0 2^0$$

is encoded into a modified representation of the form

$$B = B_m 2^{3m} + B_{m-1} 2^{3(m-1)} + \dots + B_1 2^3 + B_0 2^0$$

where $m = \lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil$. Thus, the number of partial products is reduced by a factor of three from fifty-four to eighteen.

Figure 2: FPM Mantissa Section

Each partial product is formed by multiplying the multiplicand and a Booth coefficient which can be $\pm 4, \pm 3, \pm 2, \pm 1, 0$ as determined by encoding overlapping sets of four multiplier bits. The Booth coefficients 4, 2, and 1 correspond the shifting the multiplicand by 2, 1, and 0 respectively. The Booth coefficient 0 corresponds to a zero partial product. The Booth coefficient 3 presents a little bit of a problem (in fact, it is probably the reason that octal Booth encoding has not, to our knowledge, been used in building fast parallel multipliers before this effort). The problem is overcome in this multiplier by precomputing three times the multiplicand; thus this part of the operation need only be performed once for the entire multiplication. This leaves only the negative coefficients. These are handled by a two's complement operation. The bits generated for negative Booth's coefficients are inverted and an additional bit corresponding to incrementing the complemented number is generated and treated as another partial product bit.

The mantissa multiplier consists of an array of el-

ements containing a multiplexor which determines the correct partial product bit and a carry-save adder which accumulates the partial product. This is illustrated in Figure 1. Each row of the array corresponds to the generation and accumulation of a partial product; therefore, there are eighteen rows in the array. At the end of the eighteenth row, a long adder is required to add the final sums and carries. Both this adder and the times three circuit is implemented using the AFIT Optimized Carry Multiplex ([1]). The adder architecture multiplexes multiple carry paths in parallel to achieve extremely fast operation. A fifty-seven bit add can be completed in 5.5ns.

The entire mantissa section is shown in Figure 2. The figure shows the partitioning of the architecture to support single precision operation as discussed later. The blocks labeled "BR" (BR stands for Booth recoding) are the circuit which perform the Booth encoding of the multiplier. The B input (multiplier) is routed to the BR circuits. The A input (the multiplicand) is routed to a OCM adder for times three computation and to the mantissa array. The two OCM adders at the bottom of the array perform the final accumulation of sums and carries, as well as, rounding.

2.3 Exponent Addition

The exponent of a double precision number is an eleven bit biased unsigned integer. When two exponents are added, the bias is included twice and must be subtracted from the result. The exponent adder is implemented as a carry-select adder. The bias is 0111111111 or 1023. Rather than subtract this number from the sum of the two exponents, it is easier to add 1 and subtract 2^{10} . This is a significant simplification because it requires only a single full subtracter. The addition of 1 is accomplished by setting the carry input of the eleven bit exponent add.

2.4 Format Renormalization

Since the range of the mantissa is $1.0 \leq m < 2.0$, the range of the product of two mantissas is $1.0 \leq p < 4.0$. Any time the product is greater than or equal to 2.0 the number will not fit into the IEEE format. To reduce the mantissa to the proper range, a one bit right shift is performed. A corresponding increment of the exponent is required to retain the original value of the number. This process is called renormalization.

2.5 Exception Detection

The floating point multiplier has the capability to detect all pertinent IEEE exceptions, including:

- Invalid operation
- Inexact
- Overflow
- Underflow

An additional trap signal is generated when the number is representable by a denormalized number but is not because this multiplier does not support such number. Another extra flag is the zero flag, which is available to the user for control purposes.

2.6 Single Precision Mode

In single precision mode, the multiplier supports two parallel operations. Partitioning the exponent section was relatively easy. A second eight-bit adder was included to support the second operation. The mantissa section posed a more significant challenge. For an octal Booth encoded multiplier, there are nine partial products (half as many as required for double precision). The circuitry used to generate and accumulate the first nine partial products of the double precision multiply are used to compute the mantissa multiply for one single precision operation. The remaining nine rows of the mantissa array are used for the second operation. The least significant bits of each partial product are zero filled which, in effect, forms two 27×54 bit multipliers. The most significant bits of the two contain the desired product. A second sign bit exclusive-or circuit is also needed.

2.7 Integer Mode

In integer mode the multiplier supports one 32-bit two's complement integer multiply. The sign and the exponent units are unused. The two operands are routed to the most significant bits of the 54×54 mantissa multiplier with the least significant bits zero-filled. The result is in the most significant sixty-four bits of the results.

3 Pipelining the Multiplier

The clocking strategy for the multiplier includes two-phased nonoverlapping clocks. The logic of the multiplier pipeline is divided into five stages (see Figure 3) separated by transmission gate latches. Successive latches are controlled by opposite phases of the clock. Figure 3 illustrates the partitioning of the pipeline for the double precision mode. The first stage includes the OCM adder which is used to compute the multiplicand times three and the circuitry which generates

Figure 3: FPM Mantissa Pipeline Staging

and accumulates the first three partial products. The partial products four through nine are taken care of in the second stage, ten through twelve in the third, and thirteen through eighteen in the fourth. The last stage includes the rounding circuitry, the renormalization circuitry, and the exception detection circuitry.

It may at first seem odd that only three partial products are accumulated in the third stage, but the rationality is clear when we consider the single precision mode. Figure 2 shows that the third stage for the double precision case is actually the first stage for the second multiply in the single precision case. Therefore, time has to be allotted for the *times three* OCM adder. This illustrates one of the major difficulties encountered in partitioning the multiplier to support significantly different modes of operation. The optimum partition for the double precision mode is not the same as that for the single precision or integer mode. The final partition was achieved by minimizing the worst

case mode.

4 Performance of the Multiplier

The metrics of interest in evaluating arithmetic circuits are millions of instructions per second (MFLOPS), speedup and efficiency. Timing analysis of this design is based on extensive analog circuit simulation ([2]). The multiplier is capable of operating at 40 MHz. Thus providing 40 MFLOPS peak performance for double precision and 80 MFLOPS for single precision. Speedup is defined ([6])

$$S = \frac{t_{serial}}{t_{par}}$$

For the double precision case, a fully combinational circuit would require approximately 60 nanoseconds (ns) to complete an operation. The pipeline version achieves one result every 25 ns (when the pipeline is full). The speedup is therefore 2.4. Pipeline efficiency is defined ([6])

$$\eta = \frac{speedup}{N}$$

where N is the number of pipeline stages. Although the logic is divided into five stages, only three cycles are required to complete the operation; therefore, the pipeline efficiency is 0.8 or 80%.

5 Conclusions

A multimode multiplier design has been presented. The multiplier can perform one double precision floating point operation, two single precision floating point operations, or one 32-bit two's complement integer operation per cycle (peak). The multiplier will operate at 40 MHz providing very high numerical performance for a wide variety of applications.

References

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